

User Manual – CorrMic3 Pit Volume Ver2

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Steps:

- 0) Do not touch or clean the sample surface after ablation, this could damage the laser pits. Only use compressed air if required.
- 1) Place the sample on a glass slide and put it on the microscope stage, try to orient the sample the same way as previously used for grain acquisition.
- 2) Use the Macro 'CorrMic3 Pit Volume Ver2' and follow the instructions.
- 3) Before the fine readjustment of the reference points, make sure to have pushed in the manual switch to the eye symbol on the top of the microscope.
- 4) Align the red triangle with the 3 reference points by moving/rotating it.
- 5) Select continue to move to the 1st grain
- 6) View the 1st grain with 5x objective. Use the 1 AU channel (left) to focus on the grain surface. Change to the 20x objective and adjust the position and focus. Finish with the 100x objective.
- 7) First focus slightly above the laser pit (hit continue) and afterwards focus slightly below the bottom of the laser pit (hit continue).
- 8) Repeat this procedure for each grain. After each grain, check with the pre-ablation image of the grain to make sure that the grain names are correct.
- 9) When selecting the upper and lower limit of the laser pits use the appropriate objective (100x).
- 10) If you went through all grains, you need to change laser acquisition parameters:
 - a. Select the 'LSM laser' experiment
 - b. Change to 100x magnification
 - c. Change the frame size to 1028 to 1028
 - d. Switch to channels 1 AU (airy units?)
 - e. Use a crop area if pit volumes are small compared to the image size
 - f. If you need better quality, use an 'Averaging' of 2x (does need longer)
 - g. Save the experiment parameters

(then hit continue?)
- 11) After running a folder for each pit has been placed in the corresponding 'GrainX' folder called 'Ablation'. In there, you find the LSM stack and the derived intensity/texture and topography.

In case you do have access to **Mountains Software**, you can use the following template to derive pit volumes...

- 12) Start the program 'confomap' from the desktop. Choose Apply a template.
- 13) Go to #File/ExtractingVolume\VolumeVer3 – 30 micron.mnt
- 14) In the suitable tab, select the intensity map and then click 'Select files...'. Choose as 'Folder' and navigate to the sample folder containing all grains and activate 'Include subfolders'. In 'Filter' select as file format 'Mountains studiable' and select the option 'Select all files compatible with the selected studiable'.
- 15) Repeat step 9 for the topographic images.

- 16) Check if all files have been selected and choose the option 'Open all documents' and 'The files to use' before clicking 'OK' in the 'Apply a template' window.
- 17) The template will be applied to all pairs of files (to all grains).
- 18) Go to each document and adjust the figure 4 in the circular area that should be removed from the analysis. If detrending is not good, right click on 'level' top right – under leveling change to plane defined by 3 points. Move the points to level the grain surface. Hit ok. The circle should include the complete laser pit plus some extra area around it.
- 19) Save and close the document and repeat the steps for all documents
- 20) Use the file explorer to search for all created mnt files in the sample folder. Copy them and place into a single folder.
- 21) Now we have to extract the volumes from the documents using a 'statistical population'. In the file menu create a new statistical document. Give the name of the file and afterward select 'create a static population'.
- 22) Select all mnt files from all grains/pits.
- 23) In the 'statistics' tab click 'control chart' which will plot the volume for each pit. Right click on the chart to change the parameter to be plotted using 'observed results'.
- 24) Add another 'control chart' and plot the 'max. depth/height – hole'.
- 25) Go to the 'statistics' tab and use 'export values to a text file' to export all values.